

Promoting Assessment: Teachers' Annotations On Task-Based Language Evaluation

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Abstract. This study explored the challenges faced by teachers in conducting task-based language assessments. Employing a phenomenological research design, it aimed to understand the experiences and perceptions of eight participants. The emerging themes regarding positive experiences included promoting learning autonomy and stimulating the integration of language skills. Conversely, themes related to negative experiences encompassed managing mixed-ability learners and ensuring prompt submission of outputs. In addressing the challenges of conducting task-based language assessments, participants highlighted strategies such as providing constructive feedback, utilizing clear and effective rubrics, and offering precise linguistic terminology. Additionally, insights related to educational management included the incorporation of differentiated instruction, the importance of enhancing students' conversational skills, and the necessity of ongoing professional development. These themes suggested that integrating these practices could help teachers create more effective and meaningful learning experiences for their students. Furthermore, the findings offered comprehensive data that could inform future research with a similar scope.

KEY WORDS

1. Task-based language approach 2. communication 3. strategy

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1. Introduction

The core and essence of the human experience is communication. Human communication is primarily comprised of the four skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. These abilities show up in language. Language proficiency is acquired through language acquisition. If students want to be able to communicate and share their thoughts, feelings, and opinions with others, they should be proficient in those areas. Students must master the four language abilities, especially English, if they want to communicate with individuals from all over the world. In the global context, as stated by Xu Fan, (2022). Task-based instruction (TBI) emphasizes meaningful communication, not only fosters language acquisition but also diminishes language anxiety by providing a supportive environment for learning through engagement. Thus, TBI emerges as a pivotal approach for enhancing reading comprehension and overall language proficiency. Task-based language assessment utilizes tasks as core vehicles to activate and observe language being used to achieve real-life purposes, thereby deriving interpretations of what test takers or learners can do with their language abilities. In the early 1990s, the

field of education called for a new paradigm of assessment, widely known as alternative assessment, which measured and emphasized the ability to apply knowledge. Attempts were made to meet this goal, such as developing performance assessments. Task-Based Language Assessment is a methodology of assessment that measures the ability of language learners to express and understand meaning to achieve a specific goal or outcome within an authentic and communicative context (Norris, 2016; Norris East, 2021). In Japan, most Japanese students have studied English since an elementary school age, most recently with five years of mainly grammar-focused English instruction in Junior and Senior High School involving translating between Japanese and English. Such classes have often not involved Communicative Language Teaching approaches to second language learning, such as Task-Based Language Teaching resulting in limited chances for students to interact orally with each other in English. The Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) laid out plans in 2013 to enable students to hold conversations in English with the use of task-based instructions and assessments by the time they leave High School. However, because of the pressure placed on high school students to pass university entrance exams in Japan classroom learning focuses mainly on the content of such tests as a result, little time is left for orally interactive tasks, resulting in university students' oral English communicative competence being often limited to simple exchanges at best (King, 2012, 2013). In the Philippines, with the introduction of these two types of assessment in the academe: the written and performance assessments, educators and other advocates of learning have been clamoring about which type of assessment is effective to use in the classroom. Foreign studies have revealed the relevance of alternative assessments over traditional ones. Others even opted for an alternative assessment as their method of evaluating student learning. Most Filipino classrooms prefer to use both since one cannot be separated from the other for the reason that students need to take college admission tests as well as licensure examinations in various fields of discipline after graduation. This is evident in content courses, while skill-related subjects adopt alternative assessment as their form of assessing student learning and performance (Rosaroso Rosaroso, 2015). Tasks as organized sets of activities play essential roles in classroom learning processes. Task-based instruction is an approach that emphasizes the significance of tasks in these processes. As learners in EFL contexts have fewer opportunities to practice language outside school, classroom activities become more important (Nunan, 1989). Teachers and syllabus designers turn to the role of tasks and task-based instruction to create a more effective teaching-learning environment. Several important studies have examined the use of task-based instruction and its focus on academic competence. However, there are few research studies on the use of task-based instruction and assessment in teaching a subject area and most specifically in new normal environment. Indeed, task-based language assessment is an efficient way to gather evidence about students' conceptual knowledge, listening skills, and speaking skills. The full implementation of face-to-face classes bring forth learning gaps that was acquired through the 2-year distance learning modality. Task-based language assessment became one of the strategies that teachers employ in developing students' language skills. Hence, this study aims to explore the challenges that teachers encountered in the conduct of task-based language assessment. The researcher sought to determine the advantages and limitations of conducting such an assessment in classroom settings. In the local setting, Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte Teachers' Annotations on Task-Based Language Evaluation" consistently highlights its effective-

ness in improving communication, confidence, and specific language skills like speaking and listening. It was considered a subject of the present study because, as a researcher, I believe that Key annotations often point to the importance of culturally relevant, real-world tasks, opportunities for collaboration, and ongoing formative assessment and feedback to optimize the benefits of TBLT and overcome implementation challenges, such as teacher training and curriculum alignment. TBLT improves spoken language production, as noted in the results where speaking skills are given attention. Role-playing and scenarios of real-life communication provide practical contexts for learners to employ the target language, which is vital for acquiring communicative competence. Teachers' insights provide crucial feedback for con-

tinuous improvement, ensuring that task-based approaches lead to meaningful communication and increased student motivation. This process empowers both learners and educators by creating a collaborative learning environment focused on developing language skills in real-world contexts. Moreover, as a researcher, I also emphasize that teachers' annotations for task-based language evaluation are vital for learning development because they foster a deeper understanding of student needs, promote compelling and authentic learning experiences, and improve the overall quality of language instruction. In this regard, the researcher encourages further research to gain a deeper understanding of this topic from the perspective of other teachers in our district, thereby facilitating additional learning and opportunities.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The goal of this study was to explore the challenges that teachers face in conducting task-based language assessments. It was anticipated that the findings of this study may pave the way for the administration to accept the challenges and issues of teachers that hinder academic productivity. Such an acceptance could be utilized to improve the working conditions of teachers. It will also

visualize that the findings of this study may enable the organization to know how to address issues and challenges concerning the teachers and its working environment and to consider relevant trainings and seminars as important factors in increasing teachers' performance. These understandings would add to the academic literature of second language teachers' cognitions in a local context.

1.2. Research Questions—The primary research questions of this study are the following:

- (1) What are experiences of teachers in conducting task-based language assessment?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges of conducting task-based language assessment?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were defined for use in this study: Task-Based Language Assessment – Task-Based Language Assessment is the process of evaluating, in relation to a set of explicitly stated criteria, the quality of the communicative performances

elicited from learners as part of goal-directed, meaning-focused language use requiring the integration of skills and knowledge (Brindley, 1994). Teachers' Annotation- the thoughts or mental images teachers have about their students—are shaped by their background knowledge and life experiences.

1.4. Significant of the Study—

The findings reported in this study may have important implications for educational authorities and professional practice. Specifically, the study may inform language policy makers who are in charge of the curriculum development, of the way that the curriculum is actually enacted by classroom teachers. In this system, teachers' voices, regarding how they understand and implement the curriculum, are often unheard (Littlewood 2004). This study thus seeks to inform language policy makers by providing them with a real picture of what teachers think as well as how they implement the curriculum in a local context. DepEd Officials. The findings of the

study would give them ideas on how to enhance task-based language assessment. School Administrators. The findings of the study would give them ideas on what technical support they should give to the teachers in managing obstacles in task-based language assessment through school learning action cells. Teachers. Educational management insights formulated in this study could guide them in improving their management skills. Future Researchers. The findings generated provided comprehensive data in conducting future researches with similar or relevant scope

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on the Framework of Shulman's (1987). This framework enabled the study to capture teachers' perceptions about the curriculum in relation to their classroom task delivery. In addition, Bernstein's notion of pedagogic discourse enabled the study to characterize the relationship between teachers' perceptions and their classroom practices in the local context, particularly in relation to the three significant areas of curriculum change: curricular content, teaching pedagogy, and learner assessment. Taken together, this combined framework allowed the study to examine teachers' implementation of the curriculum from a teacher's perspective. Furthermore, another theory relevant to this study is David Kolb's (1984) Experiential Learning Theory (ELT), which builds upon John Dewey's notions about the importance of education that connects with students' lived experiences. It is also helpful for examining the relationship between mastering the curriculum

and engaging in experiential learning. Simply put, it offers a conceptual model for the experiential learning process. When the model is applied to the school context, it can be utilized as a method to meet curricular goals and objectives through approaches such as assigning performance tasks to students. Practical experiential learning is not only tied to curricular goals, but the learning experience also helps to develop competencies and skills that have life applications. Teachers can craft tasks that integrate the lesson into real-life experiences and have students accomplish them, utilizing them as a major assessment tool to generate authentic learning for students. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) challenges teachers encountered in conducting task-based language assessment; (2) coping with the challenges of conducting task-based language assessment; and (3) Insights drawn from the experiences of teachers.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption served as a framework for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data in a specific field of study. It established the background used for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions come in various types, which are elaborated below. **Ontology.** This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multifaceted as perceived by the participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, including those of the researcher, the individuals being investigated, and the reader or audience interpreting the study. In this study, the realities of teachers in conducting task-based language

assessments were explored. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants, presenting extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participants' answers to the study were coded and analyzed to identify commonalities and discrepancies in their responses. It is ensured that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher ensured the authenticity of the responses and was careful to avoid personal bias as the study progressed. **Epistemology.** This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between them-

selves and the participants. He suggests that as a researcher, one collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. This study intended to gather information from the experiences of conducting task-based language assessment. The researcher followed the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF). It was assured that there is an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Upholding the

dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants was ensured by the researcher. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants’ answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants’ interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and use qualitative terms and a limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to understand how stakeholders’ partnerships in school-initiated programs were built and maintained between schools and the surrounding community.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions—Methodology* is different from method. Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the lived experiences of teachers in the conduct of task-based language assessment were explored, particularly teachers from Dugayan Elementary School, Langilan District, Davao Del Norte Division. The researcher’s drive to know the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which is considered helpful in looking for meanings and motivations that underlie cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. By using phenomenology, it was hoped that this need would be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were pre-

sented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which is concerned with “what” and “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as a basis for possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure—*

This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design, as it focused on the lived experiences of teachers in conducting task-based language assessments. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread, and then culled for phrases and themes, which were grouped into clusters of meaning. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data, and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove himself or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were useful to follow-up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In this qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews is to understand the meaning of what the interviewees will say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file, in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews were particularly useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information around a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, which extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects that were selected into the study were individuals who have actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was be difficult to do. The researcher needed to decide as to how and when his or her personal observations were to be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were as based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasized the im-

portance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since

the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and on the perspectives of the teachers, the researcher intended to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were the ten (10) teachers from Dugayan Elementary School, Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the present position for at least 5 years- regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; (2) must be teaching English/Reading subjects; and (3) they must

have gained at least a very satisfactory rating in their IPCRF. The researcher employed a purposive sampling design, as participants were selected based on the study's criteria or purpose (Creswell, 2014). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—It plays a crucial role in the development of this research study. The researcher must address various ethical concerns related to the participants involved in this fieldwork. These ethical principles are widely recognized as fundamental to conducting responsible research. The researcher needs to follow ethical guidelines that support the study's objectives, ensure the dissemination of accurate and truthful knowledge, and minimize errors. Social Value. As a researcher, I recognize that research holds significant societal value. In this particular study, emphasis was placed on exploring the experiences of teachers to highlight their social realities. The focus was specifically on elementary school teachers. The findings aim to inform higher authorities in developing programs and policies that can provide tangible benefits to classroom teachers. The social issue driving this research is the various challenges encountered by teachers when integrating interactive media instruction into their teaching practices, to enhance their instructional competence. Informed Consent. Participants were assured that their involvement was entirely vol-

untary and based on a clear understanding of the relevant information. Details regarding the recruitment and selection of participants are included in the appendices of this report. Building trust and securing the support of participants are essential components of ethical and meaningful phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). Prior to scheduling interviews and engaging in the research process, all participants received an informed consent form. Each individual was required to provide a signed acknowledgment indicating their consent and willingness to participate in the study. The purpose of the informed consent document was to introduce the research, provide contact details, explain the study's objectives, request voluntary participation, and outline the type of information that participants would be expected to provide. Participants were asked to sign and return the consent form before fully engaging in the research process. Vulnerability of Research Participants. As the researcher, I assured the participants—who are all professional teachers in public elementary schools—that they are capable of responding to the research instrument.

I also informed them that I can be easily reached via my contact number and address should they have any questions or require clarification regarding the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. As a researcher, I ensured that the recruitment process was conducted ethically, without coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Participants were provided with the contact information of the panel chair or individual panel members should they have any questions or concerns regarding the study. Additionally, participants were informed that they were free to decline participation or withdraw at any point if they experienced discomfort or inconvenience while answering the questions, without any repercussions. Throughout the data collection process, measures were taken to ensure the safety and well-being of the respondents, including conducting the survey and interviews in a secure environment and at times convenient for the participants. The primary focus of this study aligns with the Treaty Principle of Protection,

emphasizing respect for participants' rights to privacy and confidentiality, as well as minimizing potential risks. To uphold this, pseudonyms were assigned to each informant to protect their identities, and all reasonable steps were implemented to safeguard participant confidentiality, thereby reducing any inherent risks associated with participation. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to assure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept anonymous. Furthermore, all issues were given consideration to ensure that there was no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information, as well as the representation of primary data findings in a biased way, must be avoided.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher has a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative method. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help to the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interview properly according to the design, making appropriate field obser-

vations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensured different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were properly secured as they contain sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of data. The researcher saw the phenomenon

or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding and theming. The researcher made sure that the findings are true to the participants and that their voices are heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presented the problem and the related literatures and studies that support it. Find-

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity despite the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings to implement non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following will be the step by step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapter 1 and 2 together with the research instrument which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before the conduct of it. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining about the study to be conducted in their school. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted inter-

ings of the study were presented too by research question – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, future directions and implications of the study were given by the researcher for the improvement of educational policy and practices.

oriented about the study and the process they shall go through as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data from the participants will be compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After which, the data were compared and contrasted between the participants in order to come up with patterns and trends.

views with the use of Creswell's Model specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012) themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together

to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding is also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, which involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a method of data reduction; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and a conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes is a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended

this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data, and began to define the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature. The researcher made sure that the experiences of teachers in the conduct of task-based language assessment were presented comprehensively.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The coding and categorization system within an analytical framework systematically arranges data to address research inquiries effectively. This organized approach to data analysis enables researchers to condense and summarize large amounts of information. Braun and Clarke (2022) emphasize that reflexive thematic analysis involves the researcher actively participating in the coding and theme development processes. This method requires ongoing self-reflection, where the researcher considers how their assumptions and practices influence data interpretation. The analytical procedures commonly linked to qualitative research often draw from Flick’s focus on critical practice. The widely recognized framework outlined by Braun and

Clarke (2022) includes six key stages: becoming familiar with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing those themes, defining and naming them, and finally producing the research report. The core principles of thematic analysis—such as coding data, identifying themes, refining these themes, and presenting the results—are also relevant to other qualitative approaches like discourse analysis (Flick, 2022). In essence, thematic analysis is a qualitative method used to examine data by identifying and interpreting recurring patterns or themes (Liebenberg et al., 2020; Xu Zammit, 2020). Likewise, Braun and Clarke (2022) outlined a series of specific steps involved in conducting thematic analysis within their comprehensive framework:

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability will relatively be foreign to the field of qualitative research. Qualitative researchers substitute data

trustworthiness instead of focusing on reliability and validity. Trustworthiness consists of the components such as credibility, transferability, dependability and conformability (Harts, 2016).

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study)

Credibility involves establishing that the findings of the research are credible or believable from the perspective of the participant. Through observing the attributes of prolonged engagement this is where credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the issue of credibility, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferability is the degree to which the findings can be generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job in de-

scribing the research context and assumptions that are relevant. On the other hand, dependability is the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher made sure that the findings of the study were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability is the degree to which findings can be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers. The researcher documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. The researcher also made sure that the findings are free from bias.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the results of the study are presented and discussed with reference to the aim of the study. Moreover, the themes that emerged from the data gathered were discussed in this chapter. The results present the descriptions and backgrounds of the participants, who are assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Experiences of Teachers in Conducting Task-Based Language Assessment—Task-based language evaluation is cited frequently in the literature as having significant potential for students taking Language classes (Tannenbaum, 1996). One of the arguments made in the literature for the use of task-based language assessment is that it can produce positive washback because the assessment strategy is more closely aligned with the style of instruction used in communicative language classrooms. Most people agree that assessment is an essential component of any language curriculum (Brown Hudson, 1998), and some argue that it should be taken into account when making circular decisions (Short, 1993). No matter how effective an approach is in teaching and learning, there are still underlying challenges that teachers experience along the way. These acquired challenges and experiences could potentially be added into the literature of the studies. The participants' responses were condensed into a single theme to generate subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from

informants' accounts and reflections.

3.1.1. Positive Experiences: Promote Learning Autonomy—Learning autonomy refers to the ability of learners to take responsibility for their own learning. It involves the development of skills such as goal setting, self-evaluation, and self-directed learning. For the participants, task-based assessment can promote learning autonomy because it encourages learners to become more independent and self-directed, allowing them to take ownership of their learning. Another way in which this strategy promotes learning autonomy is by encouraging learners to set their own learning goals. Using tasks that require learners to identify their own learning goals encourages learners to become more proactive in their learning. This approach allows learners to take ownership of their learning and develop a sense of purpose and direction in their language learning (Nicole, 2007). Finally, task-based language assessments promote learning autonomy by providing learners with opportunities to collaborate and work in groups. Using tasks that require learners to

work together and share ideas encourages learners to become more interdependent and collaborative in their learning. This approach allows learners to develop social and communication skills, as well as the ability to negotiate and compromise with others (Nicole, 2007).

3.1.2. Stimulates the Integration of Language Skills—Traditionally, language skills have been taught separately, with little integration between them. However, in the real world, language skills are often used in combination, and learners need to be able to use them in an integrated way. According to the participants, this strategy provides learners with opportunities to use language skills in a more natural and authentic way, promoting the integration of these skills. Task-based approach also promotes the integration of language skills by providing learners with opportunities to use language in a variety of contexts. Using tasks that simulate real-world situations allows learners to practice using language in different contexts and for different purposes. This approach promotes the development of a more comprehensive and interconnected understanding of language. As mentioned by Mann (2006), if a teacher uses a task-based approach, the language they focus on is going to be rich, and it will include all aspects of language, including functional language, the phrases and expressions that are needed to communicate something, or get something done like greeting, agreeing, reporting, asking for information, etc. Many researchers and teachers have demonstrated the benefits of integrating task-based assessment in English language skills education. They all state that learning English is more productive when students learn the four skills in a single lesson, because it is the way learners will likely use the language in their daily lives. According to Baturay and Akar (2007), integrating multiple uses of language skills is fundamental for learners to be competent in the second language and promote English learning naturally. This

integration enhances learning through constant practice and allows students to express their ideas through writing messages, understanding aural and written messages, and holding conversations.

3.1.3. Negative Experiences: Handling mixed-ability learners—Teaching a class with both quick and slow learners, also known as mixed-ability classrooms, is one of the biggest obstacles faced by teachers of students who are learning English as a second language, according to the participants' comments. Although most of the students in an English class struggle with the language, there are some who excel at it. It might be difficult to assign tasks when students in a language class have different levels of ability. It is well known that every student has a different way of learning and learns and progresses at different speeds. Thus, while some students may find the learning task easy to complete, others may find it difficult to understand. Learning also depends on what students bring to class (Kwei, 2017). Since each student comes from a different family, a different environment, and/or a different nation, the multi-cultural population of the classroom may be an obstacle for the teachers in reaching the students, which eventually results in ineffective learning. Results revealed that teachers find it challenging to strike a balance between weak, average, and fast learners, as weak students tend to feel demotivated and develop an inferiority complex, and this affects participation in class. Hordiinko and Lomakina (2015) noted that weak students tend to lack basic knowledge of the subject, and this makes them feel frustrated when in mixed-ability classrooms. A similar result was generated by the study of Svärd (2006) wherein he interviewed secondary teachers in an attempt to investigate challenges faced by English teachers when teaching mixed-ability classes and ways to overcome these challenges. Challenges of teaching mixed-ability classes were identified as dealing with learners with different learning

abilities; difficulty of getting attention from all learners; poor motivation by learners; frustration on the part of the teacher; uncooperativeness of learners; and difficulties in planning lessons and creating work material. Furthermore, according to Khasawneh (2020), there are also benefits of mixed ability classes as it gives an opportunity to accept, discuss, and listen to others' diverse perspectives. Mixed classes are useful for topic introduction, general direction, read-alouds, closure and team building. Advanced students can experience the satisfaction of helping less-able learners and modeling more complex ideas. This practice may build confidence in the advanced students as tasks require simpler skills.

3.1.4. Prompt Submission of Output—One of the obstacles to effective task-based language assessment is the submission of the output. According to the participants, there are students who submit their task outputs late, or worse, those who fail to submit. Based on the responses, students' motivation and interest in making the tasks is a contributory factor. Students often put more value on what is happening today than on what will happen tomorrow. This can make working on homework and tasks something they push off until they absolutely must. Pair that with the fact that many students dislike the idea of doing schoolwork at home, and this is the perfect recipe for a procrastination problem (Oswell, 2013). Procrastination can hurt students' schoolwork, grades, and even their overall health. Students who procrastinate experience higher levels of frustration, guilt, stress, and anxiety—in some cases, leading to serious issues like low self-esteem and depression. The effects of procrastination can have an even bigger impact on high school students. Once students reach high school and start receiving more tasks and larger projects, students who procrastinate until the last minute tend to receive lower grades than their peers (Oswell, 2013). Moreover, another contributory factor to this ob-

stacle is the internet connection and the lack of resources on the part of the students. According to the participants, some tasks require internet surfing, cameras, and the like. There are students who have limited internet access, which is why most of them are not submitting the needed tasks. One of the biggest problems faced by students without internet access at home is their inability to complete homework. While it may seem like almost everyone has internet access, a shocking number of families lack fast or reliable internet connections. There are roughly 5 million households with school-age children who don't have broadband internet access at home. That means millions of students are being left behind. There are many ways that a lack of internet access can affect a student's academic performance. Students without internet can't connect with teachers or classmates, do independent research, or get online help. For families, not having internet access can mean missing out on information or losing out on a direct line of communication with schools and teachers (Lynch, 2017). The social and economic challenges that were haunting the country at the time of the study did not spare the students and the participants in this study, who confirmed that social and economic factors were a real issue that affected their progress. The findings of this study generally demonstrate the importance of constant close monitoring of students' progress in the open and distance learning institutions. The monitoring would be more effective if it were applied to students, where obstacles to progress could be addressed in time. In relation to this note, Zainal and Mel (2007) point out that teachers are concerned with the mechanics of ensuring that the student makes good progress towards completion of the task-based assessment.

3.1.5. Handling Mixed-Ability Learners—Addressing the needs of learners with diverse abilities requires implementing adaptable approaches such as tailored instruction, diverse

grouping methods, and customized activities. These strategies help accommodate individual differences while promoting collaboration and an inclusive learning environment. According to Xiao, (2020), although student factors, administrative decisions, contexts, and financial-related factors may also contribute to its existence, the teacher factor is the most relevant factor when discussing the challenges of teaching mixed-ability classes. However, those who are affected the most by mixed-ability classrooms are teachers and students. Moreover, the random grouping of students by age may not prevent mixed-ability students from being in the same class (Kotob Abadi, 2019). An explanation of the mixed-level condition to students and give a list of possible approaches to teaching and learning should be given. In pairs, students number the ideas according to their suitability. By developing strategies and writing a standard practice for activities, the teacher can increase the sense of belonging in the class Gwozdz, (2020). Hence, the importance of using flexible teaching methods, such as personalized instruction, varied grouping strategies, and tailored activities, to effectively support learners with different abilities. These approaches help address individual needs while fostering col-

laboration and inclusivity in the classroom. It also notes that these diverse classrooms have the most impact on students and teachers. Additionally, random grouping by age may not always prevent students of different ability levels. It is suggested that teachers explain the mixed-level situation to students and provide a list of teaching strategies. The figure 3 shows the emerging themes on the experiences of teachers in conducting task-based language assessments. The themes on the positive experiences were promotes learning autonomy and stimulates the integration of language skill. At the same time, the themes on the negative experiences were handling mixed-ability learners, and prompt submission of output. These themes implied that task-based language assessment uses language in authentic contexts, and helps students stay motivated and engaged throughout the learning process. It can be an effective approach to language instruction, but it requires careful planning and implementation to address the challenges that may arise, such as handling mixed-ability learners and unprompted submission of output. By providing appropriate support, feedback, and assessment, teachers can help learners achieve their learning goals and develop the skills they need to succeed.

*3.2. Coping with the Challenges of Conducting Task-Based Language Assessment—*Task-based language assessment has been gaining popularity in recent years as an effective method of teaching language. This involves learners engaging in tasks that simulate real-world situations where they use the target language to achieve specific goals. These tasks can vary from simple to complex, and can be carried out individually, in pairs, or in groups. However, conducting task-based language teaching can present challenges to both teachers and learners. In this section, the participants expressed their ways of coping with the challenges of task-

based language assessments. Their responses were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

*3.2.1. Giving Students' Feedback—*The purpose of effective feedback is to assess a learner's comprehension and skill development so that the next steps in reaching the learning objectives or goals can be planned. The participants thought that providing students with feedback is an important feature of task-based assessment. Feedback is a compelling influence on learner achievement. When teachers seek, or at least are open to, what learners know,

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Teachers in Conducting Task-Based Language Assessment

what they understand, where they make errors, when they have misconceptions, when they are not engaged, then teaching and learning can be synchronized and powerful. Feedback to students' performance makes learning visible (Hattie, 2009). As Pitt and Quinlan (2022) emphasize, 'Educators know that assessment and feedback practices are among the most effective levers for improving student learning in higher education (HE). Feedback is a key element of the incremental process of ongoing learning and assessment. Providing frequent and ongoing feedback is a significant means of improving achievement in learning. It involves providing information about aspects of understanding and performance and can be given by practitioners and peers. Moreover, involving parents and families in the learning process by providing them with more frequent feedback about their child's learning progress and strategies they can use to assist their child's improvement has been shown to be effective in improving student achievement (Reynolds, 2013).

3.2.2. Making Use of Clear and Good Rubrics—Assessing student performance in an English classroom is one of the biggest concerns educators faces. The increasing emphasis on competency means that educators must devise methods that measure proficiency and the ability to perform. According to the participants, in order to cope with these concerns, they ensured to conduct assessments based on the students' actual performance with a very clear measurement rubric; they noticed some increase in students' motivation and performance. Unlike more traditional tests, tasks-based assessments do not have clear-cut right or wrong answers. Instead, there are degrees to which the student is successful or unsuccessful. Rubrics need to take those varying degrees into consideration. A rubric should be thought of as a rating system to determine the proficiency level at which a student is able to perform a task or display knowledge of a concept. With rubrics,

it is possible to define the different levels of proficiency for each criterion. When using any type of rubric, you need to be certain that the rubrics are fair and simple. Also, the output at each level must be clearly defined and accurately reflect its corresponding criterion or subcategory (Stiggins, 1994). Using clear and good measurement rubrics can also enhance the validity and reliability of assessments in task-based learning. Rubrics provide clear and specific criteria for evaluating learners' performance, and these criteria are based on the learning objectives of the task. This ensures that assessments are aligned with the goals of task-based and that students are being evaluated on the skills and knowledge that they need to develop. Rubrics also provide a consistent and standardized basis for evaluation, which enhances the reliability of assessments (Hanny, 2000). To ensure that an assessment instrument elicits evidence that is appropriate to the desired purpose, Hanny (2000) recommended numbering the intended objectives of a given assessment and then writing the number of the appropriate objective next to the question that addresses that objective. In this manner, any objectives that have not been addressed through the assessment will become apparent. This method for examining an assessment instrument may be modified to evaluate the appropriateness of a scoring rubric. First, clearly state the purpose and objectives of the assessment. Next, develop scoring criteria that address each objective. If one of the objectives is not represented in the score categories, then the rubric is unlikely to provide the evidence necessary to examine the given objective. If some of the scoring criteria are not related to the objectives, then, once again, the appropriateness of the assessment and the rubric is in question.

3.2.3. Providing Clear Linguistic Terms—Although the curriculum content primarily focuses on meaning, the participants argue that linguistic items play an important role in task-

based language assessment. Based on their experiences, the teacher-participants suggest that teachers implementing task-based language assessment should consider integrating attention to linguistic form. For students to achieve the objectives of the tasks, teachers should clear up any linguistic difficulties students are experiencing such as vocabulary and grammar. For the participants, it is beneficial as it improves all areas of communication like listening, speaking, reading, and writing. According to the participants, linguistic items should be presented in the first stage so that students can use these items for subsequent activities. This is in accordance with other teachers' comments on the pre-task stage in the sequence of tasks which emphasize teaching linguistic items at the start of the lesson. As such, there appears to be a general similarity of opinion among the participating teachers that presentation of linguistic items is necessary in the classroom and that the pre-task stage serves this purpose. Many different facilitative tools can be utilized in providing linguistic items to them. Among them are breaking the task into smaller, more manageable parts; using 'think aloud, or verbalizing thinking processes when completing a task; cooperative learning, which promotes teamwork and dialogue among peers; concrete prompts, questioning; coaching; cue cards or modeling. Others might include the activation of background knowledge, giving tips, strategies, cues

and procedures. Teachers must be mindful of keeping the learner in pursuit of the task while minimizing the learner's stress level. Skills, or tasks too far out of reach can lead a student to his frustration level, and tasks that are too simple can cause much the same effect (West, 2015). Indeed, teachers need to help students master some linguistic skills to independently perform. Teachers must help with only those skills that are beyond the student's capability. Of great importance is allowing the student to complete as much of the task as possible, unassisted. Student errors are expected, but, with teacher's feedback and prompting, the student can achieve the tasks. When the student takes responsibility for the task, the teacher begins the process of fading, or the gradual removal of the scaffolding, which allows the student to work independently (Benson, 1997). The figure below shows the emerging themes from the responses of the participants which were giving students' feedback, making use of clear and good rubrics, and providing clear linguistic terms. These practices have several implications for both teachers and learners, including promoting a supportive and positive classroom culture, enhancing learners' motivation and engagement in task-based assessments, and fostering long-term language development. By incorporating these practices into the approach, teachers can create a more effective and meaningful learning experience for their learners.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study—The participants shared the educational management insights that were drawn from their experiences. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

3.3.1. Incorporation of Differentiated Instruction—One of a teacher's duties is to create an assessment experience that enables each student to exhibit his or her learning while considering the individual interests, learning preferences, and needs. Students have varied learning needs. Teachers can achieve this goal with the aid of task-based assessment. The participants held that teachers may differentiate task-based assessments for all students using a variety of

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on Coping with the Challenges of Conducting Task-Based Language Assessment

techniques, even though, in some cases, students with disabilities may require more conventional adjustments or changes to show their learning. The goal of incorporating differentiated instruction in giving task-based assessment is to create learning opportunities that make allowances for differences in how individual students learn in order to ensure equal access to important academic content. Content may be modified for students who need additional practice with essential elements before moving on; however, the expectation is that modifications in other areas will ultimately allow all students to master the same key content (Ford, 2015). In this type of strategy in task-based assessment every student is not learning something different; they are all learning the same thing, but in different ways. And every student does not need to be taught individually; differentiating instruction is a matter of presenting the same task in different ways and at different levels, so that all students can approach it in their own ways (Trujo, 2004). The effectiveness of this approach requires ongoing evaluation of students'

needs and conscious attention to designing task-based assessments to meet those needs. It is true that teachers must have an extensive repertoire of research-based instructional strategies at hand, but they must also be able to think outside the box to ensure that each student's needs are met. As Tomlinson and Imbeau (2010) point out, the teacher's role in the classroom is to continually ask him/herself what students need at the moment to be able to progress with this key content, and to how they can make it happen.

3.3.2. Importance of Improving Students' Conversational Skills—The participants' answers supported the claim that the ultimate objective of teaching English is the development of students' communicative abilities, and that task-based evaluation is a useful tool for achieving this goal. The data was replete with comments that highlighted the importance of developing communicative skills. These teachers seem to consider the provision of task-based assessments as a prerequisite to developing communicative skills. In a classroom-based study in Vietnam, Viet (2013) found that teachers often

taught students through concept application in order for them to develop communicative skills, thus, this suggest a structural approach to the development of learning. The interview data in the current study supports Viet's findings, demonstrating the prevalence of a structural approach in relation to the implementation of the curriculum. Additionally, these results align with observations that students tend to perform poorly in various subjects due to inadequate oral communication skills. They struggle to respond spontaneously and clearly in English when asked questions, making conversations particularly difficult. This issue was also highlighted in the research by Separa et al. (2019), which indicated that many college students in the Philippines remain uncomfortable using English, especially when tasked with recitations, reports, oral presentations, or casual dialogues.

3.3.3. Continuing Professional Development—The teaching profession today is very different from what it was 20 or even 10 years ago. The field of education develops at the same rapid pace as technology, making tactics, skills, strategies, and technologies obsolete in five to ten years. Because of this, the participants believe that being a lifelong learner is crucial to the educational process. In order to improve their students' learning progress, it aids educators in incorporating new strategies and instruments into the learning process. To be the best teacher possible, it is essential to be a lifelong learner. Lifelong learning implies that learning does not end when you leave a classroom or finish a degree. Rather, as you go through life it is essential for you to continually connect with other professionals to learn, to teach, and to share resources. Unwillingness to connect with others and to engage in the lifelong learning process leads to stagnation in your practice and will prevent you from being the best possible teacher for the children

you serve (Kimmons, 2015). This affects how CPD is enacted and practiced among teachers in Abakah, (2019), as the focus of CPD is often geared towards something else, leading to their inability to foster teacher learning. Dhaliwal (2015) emphasizes that lifelong learning aims to promote and sustain a comprehensive transformation across educational systems by updating curricula and content, as well as enhancing capacity building. The goal is to increase awareness, acceptance, and active engagement in the principles of lifelong learning, along with integrating ICT-enabled methods for instruction, learning, and assessment. Specifically, it seeks to achieve the following objectives: developing multimedia-rich curricula that are readily accessible to both teachers and students; establishing collaborative learning environments; organizing innovative and intellectually engaging faculty development programs for educators and administrators; fostering partnerships at national and international levels; and promoting education, research, and training focused on best practices and innovations in lifelong learning and ICT-based educational practices. The figure below shows the emerging themes on the educational management insights that are drawn from the experiences of the participants, which include the incorporation of differentiated instruction, the importance of improving students' conversational skills, and continuing professional development. These themes imply that these are the essential aspects of modern teaching practices. By incorporating task-based teaching into the classroom, teachers can help learners develop their conversational skills and communicative competence in a meaningful and effective way. Continuing professional development is crucial for integrating task-based teaching into the classroom and ensuring that teachers have the knowledge and skills they need to support learners effectively.

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter provides a brief overview of the study, followed by implications drawn from its findings. Future directions in the field of technology leadership of principals are also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—The goal of this study was to explore the challenges that teachers face in conducting task-based language assessments. The emerging themes on the positive experiences of teachers in conducting task-based language assessments were promoting learning autonomy and stimulating the integration of language skills. At the same time, the themes on the negative experiences were handling mixed-ability learners and prompt submission of output. These themes implied that task-based language assessment uses language in authentic contexts, and helps students stay motivated and engaged throughout the learning process. It can be an effective approach to language instruction, but it requires careful planning and implementation to address the challenges that may arise, such as handling mixed-ability learners and un-

prompted submission of output. By providing appropriate support, feedback, and assessment, teachers can help learners achieve their learning objectives and develop the skills necessary for success.

4.2. Implications—On coping with the challenges of conducting task-based language assessment, the themes that emerged were giving students feedback, making use of clear and good rubrics, and providing clear linguistic terms. These practices have several implications for both teachers and learners, including promoting a supportive and positive classroom culture, enhancing learners’ motivation and engagement in task-based assessments, and fostering long-term language development. By incorporating these practices into the approach, teachers can create a more effective and meaningful

learning experience for their learners. Furthermore, the educational management insights that were drawn from the experiences of the participants included the incorporation of differentiated instruction, the importance of improving students' conversational skills, and continuing professional development. These themes implied that these are the essential aspects of modern teaching practices. By incorporating task-based teaching into the classroom, teachers can help learners develop their conversational skills and communicative competence in a meaningful and effective way. Continuing professional development is crucial for integrating task-based teaching into the classroom and ensuring that teachers have the knowledge and skills they need to support learners effectively. Task-Based Language Assessment (TBA) can be understood in relation to Lee Shulman's (1987) framework, particularly his concept of the seven kinds of teacher knowledge, to analyze and address the complexities of assessment. This connection is drawn by applying Shulman's knowledge base framework to the challenges faced by teachers in designing and implementing TBAs. It provides a framework for understanding the multifaceted knowledge and skills teachers require to effectively conduct these assessments. Shulman's framework outlines seven categories of knowledge teachers need for effective instruction, which can be applied to the challenges of conducting Task-Based Assessment (TBA). These include content knowledge, general pedagogical knowledge, curriculum knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), learners' characteristics, educational contexts, and educational ends, purposes, and values. The challenges of TBA are more apparent when viewed through Shulman's framework. Task design requires strong pedagogical content knowledge to design authentic, representative tasks that assess language ability. Assessment of performance requires deep understanding of linguistic content

and the ability to separate language use from non-linguistic strategies. Fairness and validity require detailed knowledge of learners and the specific educational context to avoid bias and ensure tasks accurately measure language competence.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, future research could explore the use of digital annotation tools to enhance assessment efficiency and effectiveness. Investigating students' perceptions of annotation-based feedback and conducting longitudinal studies may also offer deeper insights into its impact on language development. Expanding the study across diverse contexts can help identify best practices, ultimately advancing assessment strategies in task-based language education. Policymakers should promote the integration of task-based assessment strategies within classroom teaching practices. Teachers need to be provided with clear guidelines on expanding their pedagogical approaches and developing their innovative capabilities related to task-based assessments. Teachers should be empowered to revisit and modify their instructional methods to better align with the evolving educational environment. Likewise, the continuous professional development opportunities are essential for teachers to adopt modern teaching techniques, which can enhance student motivation and achievement. School Principals should facilitate teachers' professional growth by offering opportunities to deepen their understanding of task-based assessments and providing technical support through classroom observations and reflective practices. Future Researchers should replicate the current study to validate or challenge its findings regarding the impact of task-based assessments on student performance. Researchers should explore studies with larger and more diverse participant groups, including various educational levels and institutional settings.

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